

Engineering Colloidally Stable Multilayered PVA Nanocarriers via PLGA and Fe₂O₃-PLL Surface Functionalization

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1. Experimental Methods

1.1. Preparation of Fe₂O₃-Coated PVA Nanocarriers

1.1.1. Background on pH-Dependent Zeta Potential of Iron Oxide Nanoparticles

Iron oxide (Fe₂O₃) nanoparticles are widely recognized for their pH-sensitive surface charge behavior, making them suitable for applications in pH-responsive delivery systems. According to Meng et al. (2022) [1], the zeta potential of Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles decreases progressively from positive to negative values as the pH increases, with a reported isoelectric point near pH 6. This behavior facilitates pH-triggered electrostatic interactions and is advantageous in biomedical formulations.

However, in our study using Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles sourced from Sigma-Aldrich (Product No. 544884), we observed divergent surface charge behavior. Specifically, the measured zeta potential at pH 7 was approximately -30.9 mV, significantly more negative than expected from the literature. This discrepancy could be attributed to differences in surface functional groups, residual synthesis by-products, or particle aggregation states unique to the commercial formulation. Therefore, DI water adjusted to pH 7 was selected as the dispersion medium to ensure uniform and reproducible behavior.

1.1.2. Preparation Protocol

Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles were prepared for coating using the following protocol:

- Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles were prepared for coating using the following protocol:
- Centrifugation: The solution was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 15 minutes. The supernatant, containing well-dispersed nanoparticles, was retained for further processing.
- Polyelectrolyte Complexation: 1 mL of poly-L-lysine (PLL; Sigma-Aldrich, Product No. P2636) solution, also prepared in DI water at pH 7 (zeta potential: +30 mV), was added to the supernatant. Ultrasonication (35 kHz, 5 min) was applied to facilitate Fe₂O₃-PLL association through electrostatic interactions.
- Stabilization: The resulting solution was left on a rotary shaker overnight at room temperature (~ 22 °C).

1.1.3. Zeta Potential Measurement

Zeta potential was measured using an Anton Paar Litesizer 500 with a folded capillary zeta cell. All measurements were conducted in triplicate at 25 °C using disposable cuvettes pre-rinsed with filtered DI water. Sample concentrations were adjusted to ensure optimal scattering intensity. The zeta potential was calculated using the Smoluchowski approximation

1.2. Coating of PVA Nanoparticles with PLGA and Fe₂O₃

1.2.1. PLGA Coating Procedure

The surface of PVA gel-based nanocarriers was functionalized with poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA) via a self-assembly method driven by hydrophobic interactions. The steps were as follows:

- PVA Nanoparticle Dispersion: 5 mg of PVA nanocarriers were suspended in 1 mL of DI water under magnetic stirring.
- PLGA Solution Preparation: PLGA (50:50, MW ~30–60 kDa) was dissolved in dichloromethane (DCM) at a concentration of 10 mg/mL.
- Interfacial Assembly: The PLGA/DCM solution was added dropwise to the PVA dispersion under continuous sonication (40 kHz, 10 min).
- Solvent Removal: The emulsion was placed in a fume hood overnight at room temperature to allow gradual DCM evaporation and self-assembly of PLGA on the PVA surface.
- Purification: The resulting solution was centrifuged (10,000 rpm, 10 min), and the pellet was washed twice with DI water to remove unbound PLGA. The washed particles were resuspended in 1 mL of DI water.

Although the interaction between PVA and PLGA is relatively weak, zeta potential analysis revealed a shift from -10 mV (bare PVA) to -25 mV after PLGA coating, indicating successful surface modification.

1.2.2. Fe₂O₃ Coating of PLGA-Coated PVA Nanocarriers

Finally, 1 mL of the previously prepared, filtered Fe₂O₃-PLL solution was added to 5 mg of PLGA-coated PVA nanocarriers. The mixture was ultrasonicated for 5 min and placed on a shaker for 2 hours at room temperature. The particles were centrifuged and washed once to remove unbound Fe₂O₃ and resuspended in 1 mL of DI water.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Zeta Potential Characterization

As shown in Figure 1, the Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles sourced from Sigma-Aldrich exhibited a strongly negative surface charge of -30.9 mV at pH 7, differing from literature-reported values such as those by Meng et al. [1], which demonstrate positive-to-negative transitions with an isoelectric point near pH 6. This suggests a possible variation in particle size, surface charge density, or post-synthesis treatment influencing colloidal behavior.

Figure 1. Zeta-potential of iron oxide particles at different pH levels.

The zeta potential of uncoated PVA nanocarriers was measured at -10 mV. Following PLGA adsorption, the zeta potential decreased to -25 mV (Figure 2), consistent with the anionic nature of PLGA and confirming its successful attachment. After coating with Fe_2O_3 -PLL, the final zeta potential increased to approximately $+10$ mV, indicating partial coverage by the cationic Fe_2O_3 complex. However, this value is still below the $+30$ mV threshold generally considered necessary for robust colloidal stability, suggesting the need for further optimization.

Figure 2. Zeta-potential PVA, PVA-PLGA, and Fe_2O_3 -PVA-PLGA.

2.2. Colloidal Stability Assessment

Colloidal stability of the Fe_2O_3 -PLL complex was initially poor, as indicated by the broad and polydisperse size distribution and low-intensity autocorrelation function in dynamic light scattering (DLS) data (Figure 3 and Figure 4). These results imply significant particle aggregation and non-uniform dispersion, likely due to insufficient electrostatic repulsion.

Figure 3. Intensity-weighted size distribution of the PLL-coated Fe_2O_3 .

Figure 4. Correlogram of the size distribution of PLL-coated Fe_2O_3 nanoparticles.

To address this, the solution was passed through a $0.4\ \mu\text{m}$ syringe filter. Post-filtration, the DLS data showed sharper size peaks and well-resolved autocorrelation curves (Figure 5 and Figure 6), confirming enhanced monodispersity and improved colloidal behavior. Nonetheless, filtration resulted in an estimated 70% loss in particle yield, as observed from gravimetric measurements and optical density reduction. This trade-off highlights the challenge of maintaining both colloidal quality and nanoparticle recovery.

Figure 5. a) Intensity Weighted size distribution of PLL-coated Fe_2O_3 nanoparticles. b) Correlogram of the size distribution of PLL-coated Fe_2O_3 nanoparticles.

3. Conclusion

This study demonstrates a multilayer nanoparticle functionalization strategy involving PVA gel cores, PLGA coating, and Fe₂O₃ surface modification. Zeta potential trends validated successful sequential coating steps, although the final surface charge of +10 mV for Fe₂O₃-functionalized nanocarriers suggests that further refinement, such as increasing PLL concentration or optimizing incubation time, is necessary to reach ideal colloidal stability. Additionally, although filtration improved particle uniformity, it introduced significant material loss, highlighting the need for more efficient purification techniques in future formulations.

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References

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